

Geneasys KeyLab – a technical overview

The Geneasys KeyLab was not just another ‘test kit’ for genetic testing. The test kits made famous by the 2020 Covid-19 pandemic contain only the specific biochemicals required to test for a particular pathogen. Test kits require a range of laboratory equipment costing \$10,000 or more as well as complex reagents and highly skilled laboratory staff.

The laboratory equipment and reagents required for RT-PCR testing include a real-time thermal cycler, PCR plates, PCR tubes, a centrifuge, personal protective equipment, a refrigerator, an analytical balance, adjustable pipettes, AMV reverse transcriptase, Taq polymerase, PCR buffers, RNase inhibitor, and nucleotides.

Also required are forward and reverse primers and probes, but these are provided in *test kits* for various diseases.

KeyLab was a miniature diagnostic medical laboratory. It comprised all of the laboratory equipment required, plus 48+¹ *test kits* miniaturised to the size of a USB thumb drive.² The KeyLab is fully automatic,³ requiring no experience or skill to use.

Kia Silverbrook invented KeyLab to detect a comprehensive range of bacterial, viral, and fungal infections through the detection of genetic sequences unique to each pathogen.⁴

All that KeyLab needs to test for 48+ different diseases is a single \$3⁵ disposable KeyLab module and a regular smartphone or computer. A single computer can run hundreds of KeyLabs simultaneously.

KeyLab had to be cheap enough to use every time you visit a doctor’s surgery.

2012: All you need to test for 48 diseases: A Geneasys KeyLab module plugged into a smartphone or computer.

Epidemiology

Since he was about ten years old, Kia Silverbrook has considered pandemics to be one of the greatest threats to civilisation,⁶ on a par with nuclear war. One of his key objectives in life has been to do something to help counter the threat.

Keylab stored all epidemiological data ‘in the cloud’ using the capabilities of the smartphone or computer that the

KeyLab was plugged into. This would have made it the largest repository of epidemiological data in history, potentially leading to significant advances in pandemic control and disease prevention.

Every year, there are large efforts to manufacture massive amounts of flu vaccines to head off this year’s potential pandemic. But you can’t start manufacturing the vaccine until you know what the flu strain will be this year. When the flu strain originates in a developing country, it can take months before the scale of the epidemic and the flu strain involved becomes known.

Silverbrook’s plan was for there to be 100 million people all over the world administering a few billion free KeyLabs a year, each of which tests for all 198 H and N subtypes of the flu. Each of these KeyLabs reports the flu strains it encounters to epidemiology computer servers on the Internet. The world would get an early warning of new epidemics. This would give more time for the manufacture and distribution of the specific vaccine required. KeyLabs would also track the pandemic in real-time, enabling the optimal distribution of vaccines while they were still in short supply.

How KeyLab works

This is how Kia Silverbrook described the operation of KeyLab:

“You tear open a little sterile plastic foil bag and remove a KeyLab. You plug the KeyLab into a USB port on a computer or smartphone, which opens an App. An animation shows you how to take a biosample – either a saliva swab or a blood prick, depending on the type of KeyLab. You take the sample and put it in the KeyLab.

When the sample is inserted into the KeyLab, a film is pierced, and buffer fluid is released. The buffer fluid is mostly water, with a few relatively simple chemicals that lyse any cells in the sample. It also contains an RNase inhibitor to prevent RNA from being degraded by the RNases which will be present in the sample.

The lysate flows into 12 amplification chambers, where it rehydrates a lyophilized mixture of reverse transcriptase, primers, nucleotides, polymerases, and stabilisers. Nanolitre quantities of these were deposited into the chambers in the factory and freeze-dried for long-term stability without needing refrigeration.

Each chamber has four different sets of primers, so can amplify four separate target sequences of RNA or DNA. The chambers are heated by 12 thick film resistors on the PCB (Printed Circuit Board).

If RNA is to be amplified in any of the twelve chambers, it is first converted to DNA by reverse transcriptase.

Millions of copies of each target DNA sequence are replicated in each amplification chamber. Each amplification chamber can independently implement any one of the following genetic amplification methods:

Number of DNA or RNA copies required for pathogen detection

2012: The 48+ pathogens that KeyLab was designed to detect included all known human coronaviruses, as well as a generic test for unknown coronaviruses. Silverbrook intended KeyLab to include tests for all human coronavirus and influenza varieties. This chart from 2012 shows the projected sensitivity of KeyLab to various pathogens compared to commercial assays then available. It includes the four coronaviruses (HKU1, NL63, OC43 and 229E) that are among the causes of the “common cold”. In the chart above, lower is better.

- PCR (Polymerase Chain Reaction)
- RT-PCR (Reverse Transcriptase PCR)
- NASBA (Nucleic Acid Sequence Based Amplification)
- LAMP (Loop-Mediated Isothermal Amplification)
- RT-LAMP (Reverse Transcriptase LAMP)

Various other amplification technologies can be used, but the above are the primary methods that the KeyLab devices were designed for.

Each of the 12 chambers is four-way multiplexed so that 48 different target sequences of RNA or DNA (amplicons) can be amplified.

For eukaryotic cells, the main amplification target is 18S-rRNA, the RNA of the small subunit of the ribosome. This is highly conserved, and a single amplicon can often be used to identify many different eukaryotes by using different ECL (Electrochemiluminescent) molecular beacon probes. Other sequences can be amplified if required.

For prokaryotic cells, the main amplification target is 16S-rRNA in much the same manner as eukaryotes. A single amplicon may be used to detect many different bacteria. Archaea can also be detected, but as there are no known pathogenic archaea, tests for archaea are not typically included in a KeyLab.

RNA viruses are mostly detected by their RdRP gene, which is also highly conserved. Some other sequences are also amplified, such as the HA and NA genes for influenza and the N gene for coronaviruses. This allows subtyping of all influenza subtypes and enhanced detection of coronaviruses.

DNA viruses are highly varied, typically requiring different amplicons for each virus family. Therefore, a disproportionate number of amplification chambers are typically allocated to DNA viruses.

When microscopic valves are opened, the amplicons flow over the sensors. There are no pumps – the whole thing is driven by capillarity.

The LOC (Lab-On-a-Chip) is a small CMOS (Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor) full-custom chip with over a thousand integrated APS (Active Pixel Sensor) photosensors with microfluidic channels deposited on the surface. Each of the thousand photosensors has an ECL probe deposited directly over it.

Due to the immediate proximity of the ECL probe with the photosensor, no lenses are required, and about 40% of the light is captured. This compares to around 5% when using a separate photosensor as conventional systems do.

This large increase in sensitivity is significant as it allows the use of picolitre-scale biochemicals. A single millilitre of each of the expensive ECL molecular beacon probes is enough for, literally, a billion KeyLabs.

The disadvantage is that you must throw away the photosensor chip after a single use. This is practical if the entire LOC chip, including photosensors, costs only 12 cents to make. The KeyLab LOC is designed to achieve this goal.

A picolitre (a millionth of a microlitre) of an ECL probe is deposited onto the electrodes over each photosensor. There are 1,008 photosensors, each with a different molecular beacon, allowing many different tests and controls to be performed on each of the 48 amplicons.

Each of the 1,008 molecular beacons has a different DNA hairpin which straightens in the presence of a complementary oligo. Straightening the hairpin separates a Ruthenium complex reporter from a FRET (Förster Resonant Energy Transfer) quencher. The reporter is put into an excited state by an electrical pulse at the ECL electrode.

The quencher is normally within a few Ångströms of the Ruthenium, so the excited reporter emits a virtual photon that is absorbed by the quencher within a few picoseconds. This occurs before a real photon can be emitted from the Ruthenium reporter, which typically takes nanoseconds.

However, if the target DNA oligo (oligonucleotide) is present in one of the four amplicons flowing over the probe cell, it hybridises with the DNA hairpin of the molecular beacon. This straightens out the hairpin, separating the reporter from the quencher. FRET falls off with the sixth power of distance, so it is extremely sensitive to the small separation distance. When the hairpin straightens, the reporter is no longer quenched and emits a photon when it is electrically excited. The light from the reporter is detected by the APS photosensor directly under it.

The test process is controlled by a tiny microcontroller integrated into the same LOC chip. This microcontroller is also thrown away with each test and is part of the 12 cent cost of the LOC chip.

The smartphone processor is not needed during the actual test. The smartphone sets up the test process and interprets the image sensor data.

This arrangement allows a single computer to control hundreds, even thousands, of simultaneous KeyLabs, using only USB hubs. Keylab is, therefore, suitable for high throughput testing as may be required during a pandemic.

The smartphone interprets the data and determines the diseases present. In developing countries, AI (artificial intelligence) software in the phone makes medical recommendations that are interpretable by untrained people.

Due to legal liabilities, this is not practical in the US and some other countries. In those countries, the phone app provides data and core recommendations in medical terminology. It leaves the interpretation of that information up to the doctor.

The exception is if the national government protects Geneasys against frivolous lawsuits. This could be important in a pandemic, as it would allow frequent (even daily) self-testing directly by the population.

A KeyLab can only be used once. This avoids any possibility of cross-contamination with a prior test. One-time-use is economical, as KeyLabs only cost around \$1 to make.

One-time-use is also essential, as the biochemicals are used up during the test, and these form the largest part of the cost of the device. Cleaning and reloading a KeyLab would also cost far more than manufacturing a new one.”

How are the KeyLab’s price and function possible?

KeyLab is a sophisticated Lab-on-a-chip (LOC) technology that integrates the functions of reverse transcription, DNA amplification, and pathogen detection onto a single chip that is only a few square millimetres in size. Extremely low cost is achieved by:

- Forming 5,570 KeyLab LOCs simultaneously on a single CMOS⁷ wafer, making the electronics and photosensor cost just 12 cents per KeyLab;
- Using attomole quantities of the complex biochemicals required. The same amount of biochemicals that are required for a single PCR test kit can produce more than 5,000 KeyLabs; and
- Continuous high-volume production. Billions of Keylabs each year are useful in detecting endemic and childhood holoendemic diseases. This baseline production makes high quantities immediately available during a pandemic without requiring manufacturing ramp-up.

When could KeyLab have been used for Covid-19?

Even before Covid-19 had ever been heard of, KeyLab would have detected the Covid-19 virus (SARS-CoV-2) as an “*unknown coronavirus*.” This is because it was planned to have tests for all six known human coronaviruses, as well as a generic coronavirus test. An *unknown coronavirus* diagnosis is made if the generic test is positive, but all six known human coronavirus tests are negative.

While the *unknown coronavirus* diagnosis is extremely useful, it is still better to actively test for SARS-CoV-2. Starting as soon as test sequences were published by the WHO,⁸ Geneasys would have been able to manufacture over a billion KeyLabs with specific tests for SARS-CoV-2 by the end of July 2020.⁹

Every country in the world could have performed as well as South Korea or Australia, instead of as disastrously as the US. This would have saved hundreds of thousands of lives and trillions of dollars of economic disruption.¹⁰

SARS-CoV-2 is one of seven coronaviruses now known to infect humans.

Coronavirus Disease

HCoV-229E	Mild respiratory tract infections (common cold)
HCoV-NL63	Mild respiratory tract infections (common cold), (pseudo) croup, bronchiolitis
HCoV-HKU1	Pneumonia (common cold)
HCoV-OC43	Mild respiratory tract infections (common cold)
SARS-CoV	SARS - Severe Acute Respiratory Syndrome, Case Fatality Ratio (CFR): 10%
MERS-CoV	MERS - Middle Eastern Respiratory Syndrome, CFR: 35%
SARS-CoV-2	Covid-19, pneumonia, fever, shortness of breath, loss of sense of smell and taste, CFR: likely to be around 1%

The genome of SARS-CoV-2 was sequenced by China's CDC and published on 10 January 2020.

A genetic test for the Covid-19 Coronavirus (SARS-CoV-2) was developed by China's National Institute for Viral Disease Control and Prevention on 10 January 2020 and openly published on 21 January 2020. The test uses the same biochemical technology as Geneasys KeyLabs (RT-PCR), so it can be used directly in the KeyLab with minor modifications. The test shown in the table below has been modified for use in the Geneasys KeyLab.

Target 1 (SARS-CoV ORF1ab polyprotein)

<i>F primer</i>	CCCTGTGGGTTTTACTTAA
<i>R primer</i>	ACGATTGTGCATCAGCTGA
<i>Probe</i>	SA-RU-FS- CCGTCTGCGGTATGTGGAAGGTTATGG-PS-Q

Target 2 (N)

<i>F primer</i>	GGGGAAGTCTCTCTAGAAAT
<i>R primer</i>	CAGACATTTTGTCTCAAGCTG
<i>Probe</i>	SA-RU-FS- TTGCTGCTGCTTGACAGATT-PS-Q

SARS-CoV-2 tests developed by a private company in Germany were published by the World Health Organisation (WHO) on 13 January 2020 and form the basis of the WHO test kits.

The test also uses RT-PCR, so it can also be used directly in the KeyLab with minor modifications. The test shown in the table below has been modified for use in the Geneasys KeyLab.

Target 1 (RdRP gene)

<i>F primer</i>	GTGARATGGTCATGTGTGGCGG
<i>R primer</i>	CARATGTTAAASACTATTAGCATA
<i>Probe 1</i>	SA-RU-FS- CCAGGTGGWACRTCATCMGGTGATGC-PS-Q
<i>Probe 2</i>	SA-RU-FS- CAGGTGGAACCTCATCAGGAGATGC-PS-Q

Target 2 (E gene)

<i>F primer</i>	ACAGGTACGTTAATAGTTAATAGCGT
<i>R primer</i>	ATATTGCAGCAGTACGCACACA
<i>Probe</i>	SA-RU-FS- ACACTAGCCATCCTTACTGCGCTTCG-PS-Q

Target 3 (N gene)

<i>F primer</i>	CACATTGGCACCCGCAATC
<i>R primer</i>	GAGGAACGAGAAGAGGCTTG
<i>Probe</i>	SA-RU-FS- ACTTCTCAAGGAACAACATTGCCA-PS-Q

Other tests were subsequently published.¹¹

All of these tests could be easily adapted to the KeyLab and added to the KeyLab's array of tests. This is because KeyLab uses the same genetic test technology as these Covid-19 tests, RT-PCR,¹² and was already designed to detect all known human coronaviruses. Extra coronavirus tests are straightforward to add.

"Once again, Our key message is: test, test, test."

WHO Director-General Tedros Adhanom Ghebreyesus - 16 March 2020

Tests kits for Covid -19 were famously in short supply¹³ across the world for many months into the pandemic. The main reason is that test availability was limited by the amount of complex DNA-based reagents, called primers and probes, that could be chemically synthesised. These could not be stockpiled beforehand, as they are specific to SARS-CoV-2 and could not be made until suitable DNA sequences for the primers and probes were known.

To specifically test for Covid-19, instead of detecting it as *unknown coronavirus*, Geneasys staff would have had to wait until suitable primer/probe sequences were published,¹⁴ the first of which was on 13 January 2020. From there, it would have taken Geneasys two days to add a specific SARS-CoV-2 test to the 5.5 million daily production of KeyLabs.¹⁵

Test accuracy

The accuracy (sensitivity and specificity) of the *test kits* currently in use to detect Covid-19 is remarkably high. The KeyLab test accuracy is essentially the same, as KeyLabs use the same genetic technology.

<i>Factor</i>	<i>"Test kits."</i>	<i>Keylab</i>
<i>Sample</i>	Nasopharyngeal swab	Saliva swab
<i>Biotechnology</i>	RT-PCR	RT-PCR
<i>RNA-DNA</i>	AMV reverse transcriptase	AMV reverse transcriptase
<i>Amplification</i>	PCR	PCR
<i>DNA detection</i>	DNA probes	DNA probes
<i>Probe sequences</i>	WHO	WHO
<i>Probe type</i>	fluorescent probes	ECL molecular beacons
<i>DNA Copies</i>	~1,000,000,000	~1,000,000

KeyLab uses saliva swabs instead of painful nasopharyngeal swabs. Nasopharyngeal swabs are not suitable for personal home use and are very problematic for use on children. Saliva swabs have been found to be just as effective for many diseases and better for some, including Covid-19.¹⁶

Each KeyLab only makes around one million copies of each target DNA sequence, while typical bulk PCR tests make around a billion copies. However, KeyLab is around a thousand times more sensitive to the number of target-probe hybridisations,¹⁷ so the overall test sensitivity is equivalent.

The genetic RNA of a virus or ribosomal RNA of a cell is first converted to DNA by reverse transcriptase. Then the resulting DNA is amplified by PCR to around a million copies (KeyLab) or a billion copies (Covid-19 test kits). A single molecule of RNA can be amplified and detected by

either technology, though in general, more RNA is required for reliable results.

Cost, price, and quantity

Kia Silverbrook had intended that the manufacturing cost of KeyLabs would be below US\$1 each in billion quantities per year. At a price of around \$3 each to wealthy countries and free to developing countries, KeyLabs would be substantially cheaper than the \$25 to \$100¹⁸ price of the Covid-19 test kits that were used in 2020.¹⁹

Geneasys KeyLabs could be rolled out at roughly 5,000 times the rate of Covid-19 test kits, as KeyLabs only use attomole quantities of primers and probes. The same effort that it took to synthesise the primers for a thousand Covid-19 test kits would produce enough for five million KeyLabs.²⁰

However, the Geneasys KeyLab was not a total panacea. Geneasys would have been able to produce only a billion Covid-19 KeyLabs in the first six months of the pandemic. While vastly better than the testing disaster of 2020, this is still not nearly enough to test everybody. For that, around eight times as many KeyLabs would be required. This would have required greater investment in Keylab factory capacity than Silverbrook was able to fund by himself.

Delay in test results

The time from taking a sample swab and getting the results back is also vitally important. After taking a sample using a Covid-19 test kit, the swab usually had to be sent to an off-site pathology lab, where the transport delays and test queues typically took days. Any delay increases the amount of contact tracing that must be done. A delay beyond a few days largely eliminates the value of testing for pandemic control.

Even six months into the pandemic, it was common for tests to take a week or more, especially in the US.²¹

With KeyLab, the total delay is around 45 minutes. The swab is directly placed in the KeyLab,²² which immediately performs the test while the patient waits for the result.

Early detection is also important for treatment. In the pre-symptomatic stage, typically up to a week before the onset of symptoms, antiviral drugs are the appropriate therapy. As the infection advances, the most effective therapy changes from antiviral to immunomodulatory therapies to block the effects of an overactive immune system. The delay in test results meant that it was typically already too late for antiviral drugs by the time people were diagnosed. People presenting to hospitals were already far sicker than they needed to be.

The advantages of having many tests in each KeyLab

A vitally important aspect of KeyLab is that it tests for multiple pathogens simultaneously. The 2014 version of KeyLab had twelve separate amplification chambers, each capable of either PCR or isothermal amplification. Each chamber was 4-way multiplexed with primers, allowing 48 distinct DNA sequences to be amplified.

Many pathogens, such as the RNA viruses influenza and coronavirus, must be detected from RNA sequences.

Prokaryotes such as bacteria carry their genomes in DNA rather than RNA. Even then, it is often easier to detect the type of bacteria from its ribosomal RNA (typically 16S rRNA), which may be thousands of times more abundant than DNA. The same can be true for eukaryotes such as protists, where the identity of the pathogen can also be detected from its ribosomal RNA (typically 18S-rRNA).

Incorporating many tests has numerous advantages over an exclusively Covid-19 test:

- it provides an alternative diagnosis if Covid-19 is negative – this gives greater confidence in the test result, as well as information for alternative treatment;
- it can detect unknown coronaviruses and influenza viruses before they are identified and sequenced;
- incorporating RT-PCR, Isothermal, and antibody tests gives greater confidence in clear-cut cases and can detect a wider range of marginal cases;
- earlier detection of Covid-19 is possible, as people who thought they had the flu would be automatically tested for coronaviruses as well. Therefore, the presence of Covid-19 in a region could be determined before anyone had any suspicion of infection;
- production and distribution of tests that can specifically detect new pandemic pathogens can be immediately ramped up into multiple millions per day. A new test is simply added to KeyLabs already being produced and distributed at a rate of several billion units per year;
- it provides extensive epidemiological data on multiple infectious diseases;
- the development cost is justified by applicability to many markets;
- the test units are kept in continuous production in years when there is no pandemic; and
- unlike test kits, KeyLab unit costs fall rapidly with production volume. Extensive free distribution to developing countries helps to drive unit costs down.²³

How many diseases can be detected?

KeyLab is specified to detect 48+ different diseases. However, it is not as simple as that, as Keylab is specifically designed for subtyping pathogens and detection of pathogen families. For example, detecting and subtyping all 168 H_xN_y known potential subtypes of type-A influenza (such as H1N1, H9N2, etc.) requires only half of one of Keylab's 12 independent amplification chambers.

Each amplification chamber is multiplexed with four sets of forward and reverse primers for a total of 48 amplified genetic sequences.

The main sequences amplified to detect a wide range of pathogens are:

- 18s rRNA (ribosomal RNA) for eukaryotes (plants, animals, and fungi, and including, including single-celled eukaryotes such as algae, protozoans, and yeasts)
- 16s rRNA (ribosomal RNA) for prokaryotes (bacteria and archaea)

- RdRp (RNA dependant RNA polymerase) for detecting a very large variety of RNA viruses such as coronavirus, noroviruses.
- HA and NA genes of type A influenza, allowing subtyping all 168 known subtype variations.
- Varied targets for DNA viruses, depending on virus type.

Each KeyLab has 1,008 different ECL hairpin probes, 84 for each of the 12 amplification chambers.

At the maximum, a KeyLab could theoretically detect 1,008 diseases. However, this would leave no capacity for controls and crosschecking.

Genetic testing

The main focus of KeyLab is genetic testing, as these tests are very accurate, even at the early stages of a disease. If the primers and probes are correctly designed,²⁴ and if the sample is not contaminated, the false positive rate will be very low.²⁵

KeyLab makes use of genetic amplification,²⁶ where the sequence identified by primer pairs is duplicated around a million times before being detected by the probes. Thereby tiny quantities – potentially even a single molecule - can be detected.

RT-PCR (Reverse Transcriptase Polymerase Chain Reaction) is the “gold standard” for testing. It converts the virus’s genetic code from RNA to DNA. It then amplifies parts of the genetic code around a billion times, using a process that doubles the amount of DNA in each of 30 or more cycles. RT-PCR typically takes around one hour when fully automated. KeyLab is slightly faster, at around 50 minutes²⁷, as it only needs one million copies, taking 20 cycles instead of 30 cycles.

Isothermal amplification is similar to RT-PCR but continually amplifies the DNA instead of cyclically doubling it. Isothermal amplification is faster but usually is slightly less accurate. However, isothermal amplification will pick up some cases of Covid-19 that are missed by RT-PCR.

KeyLab has 12 amplification chambers, each of which can be configured to implement PCR or RT-PCR as well as various forms of isothermal amplification such as LAMP, RT-LAMP, and NASBA.

Antibody tests

However, genetic testing works best for someone who currently has the virus – they do not work as well for people who were previously infected but recovered and are no longer shedding viruses.

For this purpose, antibody tests are used. These detect the antibodies that have been produced by the patient’s immune system.

The sample for antibody testing is usually a serological sample, as the antibodies are usually circulating in the blood. However, for respiratory diseases such as Covid-19, a large number of antibodies are also present in saliva, so the same saliva swab used for genetic testing can also carry the sample for antibody testing.

Antibody tests are faster, taking around 10 minutes²⁸ instead of 45 minutes or longer for genetic tests.

Antibodies cannot currently²⁹ be amplified, so the test is not as sensitive as genetic testing – there must be relatively large concentrations of antibodies in the sample. This is true for all antibody tests.

As well as false-negative results due to the lack of amplification, antibody tests typically suffer from false positives. Even a low false-positive rate can dramatically affect the results.

For example, if a test has a typical 2% false-positive rate, this does not mean that a positive result means that the patient has a 98% chance of having the disease. For example, if the disease has a one-in-a-thousand prevalence in the community, then the chance of someone testing positive actually having the disease is only 4.76%.³⁰

Therefore, antibody tests must be used with caution. A positive antibody test should be verified with RT-PCR. KeyLab does this automatically, as KeyLab was designed to contain both genetic and antibody³¹ tests.

Again, a major advantage of KeyLab is the small quantity of antigen probes needed per test. Approximately 50,000³² KeyLab tests can be made using the same amount of antigen probes as a single lateral flow³³ antibody test.

Test quantity ramp-up

The big problem causing the slow ramp-up of Covid-19 test kits in the first half of 2020 was the quantity of complex biomolecules (primers and probes) that needed to be synthesised. Each test kit requires around 54 trillion primer molecules and 9 trillion probe molecules.

The WHO test (developed in Germany) requires the following amount of primer and probe molecules:

WHO COVID-19 test kit						
Gene	Oligo ID	Concentration	Volume	Amount	Molecules	
RdRP	RdRP_SARsR-F2	600 nM	25 µl	15 picomole	9.03E+12	
RdRP	RdRP_SARsR-R1	800 nM	25 µl	20 picomole	1.20E+13	
RdRP	RdRP_SARsR-P2	100 nM	25 µl	2.5 picomole	1.51E+12	
RdRP	RdRP_SARsR-P1	100 nM	25 µl	2.5 picomole	1.51E+12	
E	E_Sarbeco_F1	400 nM	25 µl	10 picomole	6.02E+12	
E	E_Sarbeco_R2	400 nM	25 µl	10 picomole	6.02E+12	
E	E_Sarbeco_P1	200 nM	25 µl	5 picomole	3.01E+12	
N	N_Sarbeco_F1	600 nM	25 µl	15 picomole	9.03E+12	
N	N_Sarbeco_R1	800 nM	25 µl	20 picomole	1.20E+13	
N	N_Sarbeco_P1	200 nM	25 µl	5 picomole	3.01E+12	
Total primers					5.42E+13	
Total probes					9.03E+12	

By contrast, a KeyLab only requires around 10 billion primer molecules and 4 million probe molecules per test.

A KeyLab equivalent of the WHO Covid-19 test requires the following amount of primer and probe molecules to achieve the same test performance:

COVID-19 section of KeyLab (using modified WHO tests)					
Gene	Oligo ID	Concentration	Volume	Amount	Molecules
RdRP	RdRP_SARSr-F2	0.6 nM	5 µl	3 femtomole	1.81E+09
RdRP	RdRP_SARSr-R1	0.8 nM	5 µl	4 femtomole	2.41E+09
RdRP	RdRP_SARSr-P2	1800 nM	1 pl	1.8 attomole	1.08E+06
RdRP	RdRP_SARSr-P1	1800 nM	1 pl	1.8 attomole	1.08E+06
E	E_Sarbeco_F1	0.4 nM	5 µl	2 femtomole	1.20E+09
E	E_Sarbeco_R2	0.4 nM	5 µl	2 femtomole	1.20E+09
E	E_Sarbeco_P1	1800 nM	1 pl	1.8 attomole	1.08E+06
N	N_Sarbeco_F1	0.6 nM	5 µl	3 femtomole	1.81E+09
N	N_Sarbeco_R1	0.8 nM	5 µl	4 femtomole	2.41E+09
N	N_Sarbeco_P1	1800 nM	1 pl	1.8 attomole	1.08E+06
Total primers					1.08E+10
Total probes					4.34E+06

This means that around five thousand times as many KeyLab tests can be made with the same quantity of SARS-CoV-2 primers.

Comparison of the amount of primers (WHO/KeyLab) 5,000

Five million KeyLabs a day could be produced using the same amount of Covid-19-specific biomolecules as are needed to make only one thousand test kits a day.

Also, around two million times as many KeyLab tests can be made with the same quantity of SARS-CoV-2 probes.

Comparison of the amount of probes (WHO/KeyLab) 2,083,333

This helps reduce the cost of KeyLabs, as probes are expensive.

Software

Much of the effort on the Geneasys technology was to be in developing software running on the smartphone. As Silverbrook said:

The Geneasys KeyLab – 48+ fully automatic PCR genetic tests in a USB key.

2012: exploded view of a Geneasys KeyLab. The 48 genetic tests are simultaneously performed by the tiny Lab-on-a-chip (LOC)

“If you want to enable 100 million villagers to become instant doctors, it also had to be incredibly simple to use and require no training. For this, it needed very sophisticated software.”

Manufacturing

The most sophisticated part of KeyLab manufacture is the standard CMOS wafers. As KeyLab deliberately does not require leading-edge CMOS,³⁴ there are dozens of companies worldwide that can produce the custom wafers required, at US\$635 per wafer³⁵ or less. As each wafer contains around 5,570 KeyLab LOCs,³⁶ the LOC chips only contribute around 12 cents to the KeyLab manufacturing cost. Suitable wafer fabs³⁷ exist in many countries, including Taiwan, China, Singapore, South Korea, Germany, Israel, and the USA. There are none in Australia.

KeyLabs also require a purpose-built factory containing clusters of standard equipment as well as some purpose-built machines. This factory tests the incoming CMOS wafers, processes the wafers, adds some low-cost parts, deposits all of the biochemicals required, adds the plastic shell, and tests the KeyLabs. The KeyLabs are then packaged together with a saliva swab in a sterile “pillow” flow package.³⁸

The plan for the purpose-built factory was for it to be a fully automated,³⁹ semiconductor-clean⁴⁰, and sterile factory of moderate complexity able to produce 6 billion KeyLabs a year when fully populated with equipment. It could be located almost anywhere in the world as it did not require low-cost labour, just highly educated engineers and scientists.

It is essential that the clean-room minienvironments are sterile. If DNA or RNA from humans having any of the 48+ diseases detected by a KeyLab is accidentally incorporated into a KeyLab, there is a chance that it could be amplified by the KeyLab and give false-positive readings.

To ensure that this does not happen, the wafers, LOCs, and other components are processed with atmospheric downstream oxygen plasma generators directly before biochemical deposition. Downstream oxygen plasma generates a stream of single oxygen atoms. These are highly reactive and will destroy all organic contaminants.

2012: Geneasys KeyLab LOC chip layout – 5 mm long. This only shows the chip’s MEMS layout – the chip’s CMOS layers contain a few million transistors.

Vaccines

Vaccines are the most critical technology needed to combat a new pandemic. As of 20 July 2021, 143 Covid-19

vaccine candidates were being developed worldwide. Of these, 32 were in phase 3 trials, 11 were authorised for limited use limited, and 8 were approved for full use.⁴¹

Vaccines are now broadly available in many wealthy countries. However, in some countries such as the US, anti-vaxxers have been very vocal, and vaccine uptake is stalling at levels insufficient to achieve herd immunity.

Patents

To protect the Geneasys project, Kia Silverbrook filed 355 patent families⁴² on the inventions that KeyLab is based around. Silverbrook patented the Geneasys inventions in 2011 to ensure that potential patent action from incumbent companies could not stop the humanitarian aspects of the Geneasys project.⁴³ Geneasys’s portfolio was one of the strongest patent portfolios in the field.⁴⁴ All of these patents are now in the public domain, and anyone can use the inventions they describe.

When will the next pandemic occur?

Silverbrook’s efforts are now too late to make a difference in the Covid-19 pandemic. However, his renewed efforts could be ready for the next significant pandemic.

When will this be? One might suspect that it will be in around a hundred years, as it was around a hundred years between the 1918-1919 “Spanish flu”⁴⁵ and the 2020 coronavirus pandemic.

However, Silverbrook believes that the next pandemic may occur much sooner. In 2020, terrorists and rogue states such as North Korea learned that even a relatively mild⁴⁶ pandemic can have a greater societal and economic impact on the US than the largest nuclear attack that North Korea could hope to muster.

Modern technology has made it relatively easy to create new viruses to order. It is particularly easy to mutate influenza into new variants, as the flu genome is composed of 8 small independent strands of RNA which can be reassorted between flu serotypes (e.g., H1N1, “Spanish flu” or H7N9, a 2018 flu) to create a new serotype, without relying on the highly inefficient process of random genetic mutation. This happens naturally, and

reassortment is also regularly used in the production of flu vaccines.

The biotechnology required is within the grasp of terrorists and is vastly easier than building nuclear bombs. How long will it be until they do it? Silverbrook is concerned that it could be much less than another 100 years and that a deliberately engineered pathogen could be ten times as virulent as Covid-19.

If an engineered coronavirus had the transmissibility of the Delta variant of SARS-CoV-2 but the virulence of MERS-CoV, it might be 35 times worse than Covid-19.

Thankfully, it is not so easy to develop a new virus with greater virulence. Evolution has had hundreds of millions of years in an ‘arms race’ between viruses and animals to develop and combat the current level of virulence. However, it is getting easier every year as biotechnology advances. Synthetic viruses are also dramatically easier than synthetic bacteria, as they do not need to be alive.

In its September 2019 annual report, the World Health Organization’s Global Preparedness Monitoring Board wrote:

“The world is not prepared for a fast-moving, virulent respiratory pathogen pandemic. The 1918 global influenza pandemic sickened one-third of the world population and killed as many as 50 million people - 2.8% of the total population. If a similar contagion occurred today with a population four times larger and travel times anywhere in the world less than 36 hours, 50-80 million people could perish. In addition to tragic levels of mortality, such a pandemic could cause panic, destabilize national security and seriously impact the global economy and trade.”⁴⁷

This was shortly before the start of the Covid-19 pandemic. Luckily, Covid-19 is only around one-tenth as lethal as the 1918 Flu pandemic.⁴⁸

In 2016, Silverbrook wrote:

“Because of its H1N1 surface proteins, the 2009 variety was about as transmissible as the 1918 Spanish flu. Luckily, it wasn’t as virulent. It ‘only’ killed about half a million people. But that was just luck, and people shouldn’t be relying on luck when the stakes are so high.”

2012: Electronic block diagram of the Geneasys Lab-on-a-chip.

NOTES AND LINKS TO REFERENCES

- ¹ Kia Silverbrook's invention was a platform technology, not just a single product. The KeyLab could be programmed (by microjet deposition of picolitre DNA probes) to simultaneously detect any set of 48 infectious or hereditary diseases. The limitation of 48 infectious diseases was a compromise to keep the manufacturing cost of the first model of KeyLab below \$1 in high volume.
- Sometimes two or more KeyLabs could be used for a single patient – a first KeyLab as a 'triage' to determine if the patient had any of 48 common diseases. If the patient had, for example, the flu, a subsequent flu specific KeyLab could be used to detect which strain of flu the patient had.
- ² The KeyLab took the place of a Real-Time Thermal Cycler, PCR Plates, PCR Tubes, Analytical Balance, Pipettes, AMV Reverse Transcriptase, Taq Polymerase, PCR buffers, RNase Inhibitor, and AGCT Nucleotides, as well as Forward and Reverse Primers and Probes for 48 different pathogens. [Geneasys Overview June 2013](#)
- ³ Automated RT-PCR systems such as the Cepheid GeneXpert already exist, but cost US\$24,000 or more for the machine, plus \$42 for each disposable test cartridge.
- This automates the somewhat complicated RT-PCR process, leading to faster processing than laboratory methods - typically 45 minutes compared to 3-4 hours. Automation also reduces contamination and enables tests at point-of-care with minimally trained technicians, instead of at a laboratory with highly skilled technicians.
- The GeneXpert costs between US\$24,000 to US\$79,200 for the automated machine (depending on the number of simultaneous tests it can perform) and \$42 per test cartridge. Cepheid proves the one-time-use Covid-19 test cartridges for \$20 to eligible developing countries ([Treatment Action Group Statement on the High Price of Cepheid's Xpert Test for COVID-19](#))
- This compares to the price of around \$3 to national health services of developed countries, and free to developing countries of Kia Silverbrook's plans for KeyLab. Each KeyLab combines both test machine and cartridge into a single unit, requiring nothing other than a PC or smartphone, so can be distributed to locations which do not have a \$24,000 machine.
- ⁴ The KeyLab only performed genetic signature matches. It could not sequence DNA, nor could it perform general chemical assays. Kia Silverbrook had plans to expand the detection capability of a KeyLab to detect a wide range of cancers and other maladies, but the KeyLab would never completely replace a pathology lab.
- ⁵ The \$3 price quoted here is Kia Silverbrook's anticipated wholesale price to the national health services of Governments, where those Governments take on any legal liability. The risk of false trumped-up class action suits, such as are prevalent in the US, is something that Kia Silverbrook was not willing to take on. Kia Silverbrook anticipated that the retail price of tests intended for home use would be around \$10 each, or around \$50 for a box of ten KeyLabs.
- ⁶ Kia Silverbrook was concerned about pandemics since age 10, when he started to read science fiction. Numerous science fiction novels published in the 1950's and 1960's was 'post-apocalyptic' where the apocalypse was usually caused by either nuclear war, or a pandemic.
- In 2016 Kia Silverbrook said, *"We've been lucky lately, but that luck could run out at any time. With the extensive increase in world travel over the last century, epidemiologists are worried about a global flu epidemic that could be far worse than the 1918 Spanish flu, which killed 50 to 100 million people worldwide.*
- The 2009 swine flu and the 1918 Spanish flu were both H1N1 strains. While a person's immune system will normally prevent reinfection with a strain that it has encountered before, H1N1 was able to re-infect the world because there weren't enough people from 1918 still alive in 2009 to give us herd immunity. Because of its H1N1 surface proteins, the 2009 variety was about as transmissible as the 1918 Spanish flu. Luckily, it wasn't as virulent. It "only" killed about half a million people. But that was just luck, and people shouldn't be relying on luck when the stakes are so high."*
- ⁷ CMOS stands for "Complementary Metal Oxide Semiconductor." It is the technology from which almost all computer chips are made.
- ⁸ WHO: World Health Organization.
- ⁹ 17 days remaining in January, 29 in February, 31 in March, May and July, and 30 in April and June times 5.5 million tests a day is around 1,094 million.
- ¹⁰ The International Monetary Fund says the coronavirus pandemic will cost the world's economies \$9 trillion over the next two years. [Al Jazeera, 14 April 2020](#).
- ¹¹ Other entities, such as the US CDC, published tests on later dates, but the US CDC tests were initially faulty. The WHO test sequences were the first sequences published and were extensively used worldwide.
- ¹² RT-PCR is an acronym for Reverse Transcriptase Polymerase Chain Reaction.
- ¹³ *"In a crucial month when the American caseload shot into the tens of thousands, only hundreds of people were tested. That a biomedical powerhouse like the US should so thoroughly fail to create a very simple diagnostic test was, quite literally, unimaginable."* Ed Yong – [How the pandemic will end](#) - The Atlantic - 26 March 2020
- ¹⁴ Geneasys did not have had the ability to determine these test sequences itself, as it would have needed access to the SARS-CoV-2 virus for sequencing and testing.
- ¹⁵ As KeyLab would already have mass manufacturing and distribution channels, no time would have been consumed establishing these. SARS-CoV-2 (Covid-19) tests would be added to the spare slots of a KeyLab which was already in volume production. With practice, the two-day turnaround could probably be reduced, but Geneasys would not have had much practice, as Covid-19 would have been the first pandemic encountered by the Geneasys team. Tasks to be completed in those two days include:
- Adapting the WHO probes to the ECL system used by KeyLab. This would only take a few minutes.
 - Checking for primer multiplexing problems, such as primer-dimers, in the chosen channel of the 12 channels available. If there was a problem, a different channel would need to be chosen, or some low-priority test omitted from the KeyLab's array of 48 tests.
 - Geneasys intended to buy in most of its oligos from commercial synthesis companies. However, it was also to maintain a relatively small oligo synthesis capability for testing, research, and urgent production requirements. Silverbrook planned this internal capability to enable one-day turnaround on new KeyLab requirements, with migration to commercial synthesis without urgency.
 - Synthesizing the SARS-CoV-2 primers and probes. Only 99 nanomoles of primers and 0.04 nanomoles of probes are required each day for 5.5 million KeyLabs, so the oligo synthesis requirement is well within the capability of lab-scale DNA synthesizers.
 - Adding bottles of the SARS-CoV-2 primers and probes to spare slots in the deposition systems.
 - Programming the deposition systems to automatically start depositing the SARS-CoV-2 oligos (primers and probes) in the correct locations on the LOC and micromoulding when the rest of the preparation tasks were complete.
 - Adding the Covid-19 test to the app test tables.
 - Translating user instructions that appear in the case of a positive Covid-19 test into all the human languages supported (this would have been largely automated by 2020).
 - Adding the Covid-19 instructions and test parameters to the automatic app upgrade system.
 - Incrementing the version number of the firmware of the KeyLab (which would trigger an automatic download of the revised app).
 - Changing the graphics for the digitally printed foil flow wrapping (pillow pack) machines. This would automatically change over synchronously with all the other changes.
 - Changing the graphics for the digitally printed self-adhesive box labels to indicate that the box of KeyLabs includes Covid-19 test capability.
 - Automatically synchronizing all the changes to occur at a subsequent cardboard box changeover (e.g. at a multiple of 1,000 KeyLabs if there is 1,000 to a box).
- ¹⁶ In the case of Covid-19 tests performed in early 2020, a nasopharyngeal (NP) swab was often used. However, these are quite uncomfortable, and

often painful, for the patient, and require training to administer properly. KeyLab uses a saliva swab, which is painless and can be self-administered by patients. Of course, an NP swab could be used if desired for some reason.

Studies at Yale and elsewhere found that a saliva swab was actually preferable to a NP swab for SARS-CoV-2 testing:

“The study led by the Yale School of Public Health — and conducted at Yale New Haven Hospital with 44 inpatients and 98 health care workers — found that saliva samples taken from just inside the mouth provided greater detection sensitivity and consistency throughout the course of an infection than the broadly recommended nasopharyngeal (NP) approach. The study also concluded that there was less variability in results with the self-sample collection of saliva.

“Taken together, our findings demonstrate that saliva is a viable and more sensitive alternative to nasopharyngeal swabs and could enable at-home self-administered sample collection for accurate large-scale SARS-CoV-2 testing,” said first author Anne Wyllie, an associate research scientist at the Yale School of Public Health and a member of its Public Health Modeling Unit. She was joined by 49 other researchers at Yale on the study. [Saliva samples preferable to deep nasal swabs for testing COVID-19](#). Yale News, 24 April 2020

Famously, there were even shortages of NP swabs in the US, limiting the amount of testing that could be done in various locations in the US. Saliva swabs are much more common and are unlikely to have been in short supply.

¹⁷ The approximate 1,000 times greater sensitivity to target-probe hybridisation is due to several major factors:

- The use of electrochemiluminescence (ECL) probes instead of fluorescent probes. The ECL probes are continually electrically activated, resulting in a high rate of photon emission integrated over time.
- The extreme proximity of the probes to the photosensors (around 10,000 times closer than qPCR thermal cyclers).
- KeyLab does not require focusing optics, beam splitters, or chromatic filters, allowing much greater percentage of emitted photons to be detected.
- KeyLab has specially designed large ultra-low noise photosensors, directly coupled to the ECL probes.

¹⁸ US\$100 is the price US Medicare was paying for tests. Some insurance companies have been able to negotiate prices as low as US\$25. US\$39 is the cost of Covid-19 tests provided by the US CDC. The average cost of test kits from commercial suppliers was around US\$51. These prices do not include the other reagents required for Covid-19 tests, including complex and expensive reagents such as reverse transcriptase and Taq polymerase.

¹⁹ Most coronavirus tests in the U.S. cost \$100, but some providers have taken advantage of an unregulated health care system and insurers' obligation to cover testing, [charging thousands of dollars](#).

This is the reason why Kia Silverbrook thought it necessary to have extensive patent protection. An established company expecting to profiteer from a pandemic or from testing for ongoing endemic diseases would be seriously disrupted by KeyLab's dramatically lower prices (and much lower costs, enabling the lower prices).

Such a company would have financial incentive to try to stop Geneasys by any means possible, including patent litigation. Having a large portfolio of its own patents make it highly likely that the established company would be infringing some of Geneasys's patents or would like to license them. Instead of engaging in typically lose-lose mutual patent litigation, a cross licensing deal can usually be struck. Such cross-licensing deals are a fundamental aspect of intellectual property arrangements for most complex high-technology products. This includes any product which uses modern computer chip technology, as both the technology and the manufacturing of computer chips is heavily dependent on extensive cross-licensing.

²⁰ KeyLab's efficiency terms of probe quantities required is even better. The quantity of probes required for 1,000 test kits is enough for two billion Covid-19 KeyLabs.

²¹ *“Bae found that test results were coming back even more slowly than before, with many taking over a week. So on March 22, he posted in a private Facebook group of physicians to ask what his colleagues around the US were experiencing. The post drew over 1,500 replies. More than 40% indicated a turnaround time of seven days or longer.”*

[Why some covid-19 tests in the US take more than a week](#), by Tate Ryan Mosley, MIT Technology Review, 5 April 2020

²² No transport tube containing viral transport medium is required, as the swab is immediately transferred into the KeyLab, which contains an RNase inhibitor.

²³ Kia Silverbrook had planned for Geneasys KeyLabs to be manufactured in quantities of 2 billion per year by 2018 – 1 billion a year to be given to developing countries, and 1 billion sold to developed countries on a buy-one-donate-one basis.

²⁴ A correctly designed primer and probe set will detect DNA or RNA sequences which are unique to the pathogen being tested. The sequences need to be compared (by computer, using a BLAST search) against the entire human genome and other pathogens, to ensure that the primers and probes do not accidentally match any human or other sequences.

²⁵ This is important, as genetic testing is often used to quarantine people, or to have patients undergo a treatment regimen which may not be risk free. If the person is falsely identified as positive for the disease they may be unnecessarily placed under risk of an inappropriate treatment, or the inconvenience of quarantine. Even a 1% false positive error rate is far too high.

²⁶ Such as [PCR](#) (Polymerase Chain Reaction), [RT-PCR](#) (Reverse Transcriptase PCR, for amplifying RNA), [NASBA](#) (Nucleic Acid Sequence Based Amplification), [LAMP](#) (Loop-mediated isothermal AMPLification), and [RT-LAMP](#) (Reverse Transcriptase LAMP) and other methods.

²⁷ This is because KeyLab is more sensitive, requiring only one million copies of the amplicon (amplified DNA sequence), instead of the billion copies required by most PCR systems. This means that KeyLab requires only 20 doubling cycles, instead of 30 doubling cycles.

²⁸ The faster time of antibody tests is mostly because they don't have the time-consuming amplification process.

²⁹ Antibodies in a sample cannot currently be directly amplified - nor is this situation likely to change anytime soon. An antibody is a protein that has been translated from genetic code by a ribosome – a complex molecular machine that exists in all life on Earth.

There are no naturally occurring molecular machines which can duplicate a protein, or reverse translate a protein into genetic code. Kia Silverbrook also considers that it is unlikely that such a molecular machine will be developed anytime soon, as such a molecule will be vastly more complex than a ribosome.

³⁰ Say 1,000,000 tests are done. At a 0.1% prevalence, there will be around 1,000 actual infections present. Assume all of these are detected. However, at a 2% false positive rate, there will be also be around 20,000 false positive readings. The total positive results will be around 21,000. The chance of someone with a positive result actually having the disease is $1,000/21,000 = 4.76\%$.

³¹ From a 2013 overview presentation of Geneasys:

“Platform Flexibility – Immunoassays

Additional capability: immunoassays

- Flu detection and typing, RSV, strep A, adenovirus

Sandwich assay format

- Pre-spotted capture antibodies
 - ECL-labeled secondary complement
- No hardware design change required*
- Common CMOS circuitry for multiple applications
 - Immunoassays performed in parallel with nucleic acid assays
 - On-chip liquid control maintains fully-automatic internal workflow”
- Slide 27, [Geneasys Overview 12 April 2013](#)

³² The detection stripe on a lateral flow antibody test is about 1 mm long and 5 mm wide. The detection region above the photosensor of KeyLab is 10 microns by 10 microns. In both cases, this area is covered by the antibody detection antigen. The ratio of areas is 50,000, and the ratio of antigens required is also around 50,000. The ratio may be much higher, in KeyLab's favour, as KeyLab only requires a monomolecular layer of antigen. Conversely in lateral flow strip tests the antigen probes soak into a porous material such as nitrocellulose or sintered polymer, resulting in a three-dimensional volume of antigen probes.

- ³³ An example of a lateral flow test device is the well-known consumer pregnancy test.
- ³⁴ As at 2020, leading edge CMOS are 5 nm or 7 nm CMOS nodes, available from only three companies, TSMC, Samsung, and Intel. Cost effective KeyLab LOCs can be fabricated from anywhere from 250 nm CMOS (leading edge in 1997) to 32 nm (leading edge in 2010). For more recent nodes than 32 nm, the cost of KeyLab chips actually increases, as chip size becomes limited by microfluidics and optics, not transistor size. Chip cost is determined by wafer cost divided by chips per wafer divided by yield. Wafer costs increase with each advance in processing node, while the number of KeyLab chips per wafer does not increase beyond 32 nm, as the chip size does not shrink with process geometry (due to microfluidics and optics, as mentioned above).
- ³⁵ The wafer cost of \$635 each assumes 180 nm CMOS technology on 200 mm diameter wafers. This was the optimum process node for KeyLab LOCs in 2012, but is no-longer the optimum node in 2020.
- ³⁶ A LOC is a [Lab-on-a-Chip](#) – a miniaturised biochemical laboratory on a single “chip” of a substrate, in the case of KeyLab, the substrate is a fully functional CMOS wafer, which provides all of the control and sensing required for the lab.
- ³⁷ A “fab” is a [semiconductor fabrication plant](#).
- ³⁸ Flow packages are widely used for packaging confectionary and numerous small items. Also known as pillow packages, the package is typically made of ‘foil’ – aluminised plastic film – and is opened by tearing the package at either zig-zag end.
- ³⁹ As with most modern semiconductor facilities, the manufacturing facilities are fully automated to minimise contamination from human operators. The only people in the factory clean rooms are maintenance technicians and engineers.
- ⁴⁰ Class 10,000 with class 100 minienvironments, which is typical for advanced semiconductor packaging. It is not a biosecurity lab – the clean conditions are to protect the KeyLabs from contamination, not protect people. The operators and spaces outside the lab are in no danger, as the KeyLabs do not contain any infectious or hazardous materials. The cleanrooms therefore have positive air pressure to keep contaminants out, rather than the negative air pressure of a biosecurity lab.
- ⁴¹ Researchers around the world are developing at least 143 vaccines against the coronavirus, and 98 vaccines are in human trials according to the New York Times [Coronavirus Vaccine Tracker](#) (updated 20 July 2021)
- ⁴² The full list of 355 Geneasys patents applications filed by Kia Silverbrook at the United States Patent and Trademark Office (USPTO) is at [Geneasys patent applications](#). Patent applications were also filed under the Patent Cooperation Treaty (PCT) covering all of the Geneasys inventions on a worldwide basis. There is no such thing as a world patent, but a PCT application preserves the priority date and rights for filing patents in almost all countries, as long as national patents in each country for which patent protection is sought are filed within 31 months. A summary of some aspects of the Geneasys patent portfolio is at [Geneasys Patent Highlights - 17 May 2013](#).
- ⁴³ In 2016, Kia Silverbrook was asked “If it was a humanitarian project, why file patents?” He replied “For patent cross-licensing. The KeyLabs were intended to also be available in developed countries, where they would be low cost, but not free. Most likely in the range of \$10 to \$20 for a 48-disease test. Revenues from developed countries was how I intended to fund the large-scale donation of hundreds of millions, and eventually billions of KeyLabs.

This low price of diagnostics would bring down health-care costs, and severely affect the profitability of various large companies. These companies would try to stop Geneasys using patent infringement suits. With technology as complex as this, it is fairly inevitable that we would accidentally infringe some patents no matter how hard we tried to avoid it. We had to have enough patents so that it would be almost certain that they would also be infringing some of ours. This forces a patent cross-license, and Geneasys could continue to operate.”

Note the \$10 to \$20 quoted here is Kia Silverbrook’s anticipated retail price of a KeyLab. Most of the price goes to distributor and retail margins.

- ⁴⁴ Geneasys was ranked 3rd worldwide in Lab-on-a-chip category in [ClearViewIP - Home Health Diagnostics, Microfluidics & IP](#) ahead of Samsung, Caltech, Philips and others. Geneasys was also ranked first worldwide in Healthcare and Medicine category for 2011 in [McDermott Will and Emery - Nanotechnology](#)
- ⁴⁵ The “Spanish Flu” did not originate in Spain. However, news coverage of the Flu originated in Spain because Spain was a neutral country that was hard hit by the Flu. Other countries involved in “The Great War” censored news of the flu. Because Spain was neutral, it’s press was not politicised, and reported on the spread of the flu in Spain.
It is believed that the “Spanish Flu” actually originated in the US, as the first known case was reported at [Camp Funston in Fort Riley, Kansas, on 11 March 1918](#). This makes the US’s efforts to get China to pay the US compensation for being the origin of Covid-19 look somewhat hypocritical. The flu is estimated to have killed between 30 million and 50 million people in 1918 and 1919.
- ⁴⁶ Covid-19 “only” has a case fatality rate (CFR) of between 0.5% and 3%, and most likely around 1%, with the final value yet to be determined. SARS had a CFR of around 11%, MERS of 35%, Plague of 50%, Anthrax of 85%, and Ebola of 90%, so Covid-19 can be considered “mild” by comparison.
- ⁴⁷ Page 15 of the World Health Organization’s Global Preparedness Monitoring Board (GPMB) annual report, “A world at Risk – Annual report on global preparedness for health emergencies” at [A World at Risk - WHO GPMB annual report - September 2019](#)
- ⁴⁸ “The 1918 influenza pandemic was the most severe pandemic in recent history. It was caused by an H1N1 virus with genes of avian origin. Although there is not universal consensus regarding where the virus originated, it spread worldwide during 1918-1919. In the United States, it was first identified in military personnel in spring 1918. It is estimated that about 500 million people or one-third of the world’s population became infected with this virus. The number of deaths was estimated to be at least 50 million worldwide with about 675,000 occurring in the United States.” From page 1 of [US CDC article on the 1918 Flu pandemic](#).
50 million deaths out of 500 million cases gives a case fatality rate (CFR) of 10%. The CFR of Covid-19 has not yet been firmly established as the number of cases are wildly underreported, but so far, the CFR of Covid-19 appears to be around 1%, just one tenth that of the 1918 Flu pandemic.
“My crude presumption has been that in jurisdictions where rates of death are above 1%, there has been too little testing to capture the denominator. I think the majority of these examples can be traced back to too little testing or starting testing too late in that jurisdiction’s epidemic.” University of Queensland virologist Ian Mackay in an RACGP article published on 30 April 2020: [Why does the coronavirus fatality rate differ so much around the world?](#)